

Association between photoperiod sensitivity and basic vegetative growth phase of rice

M. Yokoo, Tohoku Agricultural Experiment Station, Yotsuya, Ohmagari 014-01, and F. Kikuchi, National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Yatabe, Tsukuba. Ibaraki 305, Japan

Vegetative growth of rice plants can be divided into basic and photoperiod-sensitive, two phases considered to be independently inherited. But experiments with isogenic lines show an association.

A series of alleles at the *Lm* locus, which belongs to the linkage group I, largely controls variation in heading time of cultivated rices. To obtain isogenic lines, individuals heterozygous at the *Lm* locus were selected during 15 generations (from F₁ through BC₄F₁₁) of a cross between Malaysian cultivar Morak Sepilai and Japanese cultivar Fujisaka 5. Fujisaka 5 was used as the recurrent parent through four successive backcrosses. Morak Sepilai transmitted the late-maturing allele *Lm^u* and Fujisaka 5 the early-maturing allele *Lm^e* to the hybrid progeny.

The BC₄F₁₀ population derived from a single medium-maturing BC₄F₉ plant showed a trimodal distribution for heading time in agreement with the segregation ratio of 1:2:1. This suggests that heading time is controlled by one gene (Fig. 1). Genotypes for three classes of heading time were homozygous early *Lm^e / Lm^e*, heterozygous medium *Lm^e / Lm^u*, and homozygous late *Lm^u / Lm^u*.

1. Heading time of 238 UC₄F₁₀ plants under natural day length conditions, Japan.

Two early and two late homozygous BC₄F₁₂ lines were tested for heading time in 8- and 15-hour photoperiod treatments. Plants were placed under natural daylight from 9 am to 5 pm. In the 8-hour-photoperiod treatment, plants were kept in complete darkness for 16 hours. In the 15-hour-photoperiod treatment, plant illumination by fluorescent lamps for an additional 7 hours was followed by 9 hours of darkness. The light intensity was 720 lux on the plant-leaf level.

Under the short-day condition, *Lm^u / Lm^u* plants headed 44 days after sowing (DS) and *Lm^e / Lm^e* plants headed 60 DS (Fig. 2). The long-day treatment markedly delayed heading in both genotypes. *Lm^e / Lm^e* plants headed 93 DS. *Lm^u / Lm^u* plants did not reach heading within 130 days, indicating that *Lm^u / Lm^u* plants are more sensitive to photoperiod than *Lm^e / Lm^e* plants.

Assuming that the two phases of vegetative growth period are controlled by different genes, under short-day conditions, *Lm^u / Lm^u* plants should have the same vegetative growth period as *Lm^e / Lm^e* plants, since they are nearly isogenic in photoperiod sensitivity. But in this study, short-day treatment accel-

2. Effect of 2 photoperiod treatments on days to heading of 2 isogenic lines with *Lm^e* and *Lm^u*, Japan. Lines that did not head within 130 days were considered nonheading.

erated heading of *Lm^u / Lm^u* plants more than it did that of *Lm^e / Lm^e* plants. This indicates that the basic vegetative phase is influenced to some extent by photoperiod-sensitive genes. A short basic vegetative phase appears to be associated with photoperiod sensitivity. ■

Rice seedling growth and metabolism in response to penicillin

A. K. Biswas and S. Mukherji, Plant Physiology Laboratory, Botany Department, University of Calcutta, 35 Ballygunge Circular Road, Calcutta 700019, India

Penicillin promoted the elongation of rice (*Oryza sativa* L. cv. Jaya) seedlings almost linearly, depending upon concentration. The promotion of shoot elongation was stronger (40% over control)

than that of root elongation (25% over control). Nucleic acids and protein contents were maintained at higher levels, with a more pronounced effect in embryo than in endosperm (see table). In the embryo, DNA was 88%, RNA was 90%, and protein was 40% more than control at 1,000 ppm. Endosperm DNA and RNA followed the same pattern, measuring about 35% over control at 1,000 ppm. Protein content exceeded that in the control by 30% at 500 ppm. This suggests that the growth-promoting

effect of penicillin is mediated through its influence on nucleic and protein synthesis.

Penicillin stimulated the activity of both ribonuclease and α -amylase (see table). The highest activity of RNase was recorded at 500 ppm (5 times control) and that of α -amylase at 1,000 ppm (35% above control).

Penicillin in the presence and absence of GA₃ was shown to influence elongation of the second leaf sheath of TN1 rice seedlings (see figure). Sensitivity of